

Hydrogen Ion Equilibria and Metal Binding Studies on Arachin

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Arachin, a protein with molecular weight 3,30,000, was isolated from defatted ground nut powder and purified to homogeneity. Hydrogen ion equilibrium studies were carried out and the number of binding sites in the protein molecule was calculated which were confirmed by calculating heat of ionization (H_{ion}) on the basis of pH measurements at three different temp. The work also reports polarographic investigation of complexes formed by copper and zinc metal ions with arachin in the higher pH range. The results show that the amino groups of arachin bind copper ions more strongly than carboxyl groups.

IN view of its important contribution to the knowledge of molecular structures of proteins and their interaction with the environment, the hydrogen ion equilibrium of protein has been studied by a number of workers¹⁻⁷. The present communication deals with the studies on hydrogen ion equilibria of arachin, which is isolated from ground nuts. The protein is edible and literature survey indicates no such studies on it.

The work also includes polarographic investigation of complexes formed by copper and zinc ions with arachin, in the higher pH range. Some of the results in the lower pH range have also been included but the binding is too weak to give useful quantitative results.

Experimental

Isolation of arachin :

Ground nuts (1 kg) were crushed finely and extracted with petroleum ether (40-60°). The defatted ground nut powder was dried in air, dipped in sodium chloride solution (10% ; 500 ml) overnight and filtered. Ammonium sulphate (A. R.) was added in the filtrate upto 0.2 saturation, when a white precipitate of arachin was obtained. It was filtered, washed free from salts and dried in vacuum (5 g). Further addition upto 0.8 saturation resulted in another white precipitate, which was of conarachin. The homogeneity of arachin was confirmed by circular paper chromatography using NaCl (10%) as the developing solvent and Solway purple (0.5%) containing H₂SO₄ (0.5%) at 60°-70°, as the locating reagent. The chromatogram showed a single violet coloured patch for arachin only. The amino acid assay further confirmed the purity of arachin. Thus, the molecular weight of arachin was taken to be 3,30,000.

Apparatus and technique :

pH meter (expanded scale) was used. The instrument was standardised with standard solution

of potassium hydrogen phthalate (pH 4.12) and borax buffer (pH 10).

Reagents and solutions* :

A 4.8% solution of arachin was used. Solutions of HCl, KOH (carbonate free), KCl (all AR) were prepared with double distilled water in all glass apparatus.

Procedure :

Varying amounts of HCl, (26.04, 17.95, 13.06, 8.34, 6.49, 3.72 and $1.82 \times 10^{-3} M$) and KOH (2.314, 4.629, 6.924, 13.887 and $23.145 \times 10^{-3} M$) were taken in 50 ml pyrex conical flasks and 2 ml of arachin solution was added to each of them. The total volume was made upto 10 ml by the addition of requisite amount of 1 M KCl ($\mu=0.15$) and water.

TABLE I—pH MEASUREMENT RESULTS (WITH ACID)

Temp. 24°, ionic strength 0.15, conc. of arachin 4.8 g/l				
H ⁺ added (Moles/1.10 ³)	pH	Free H ⁺ (Moles/1.10 ³)	Bound H ⁺ (Moles/mole protein)	Moles of H ⁺ dissociated per mole protein
26.04	1.7	19.95	420	0
17.09	2.0	10.00	488	0
13.06	2.1	7.94	353	67
8.34	2.3	5.011	229.1	190.9
6.49	2.4	3.981	173.1	246.8
3.72	2.6	2.512	83.45	336.5
1.82	3.0	1.0	56.55	363.45
0.00	6.5	0.0003	0	420

pH MEASUREMENT RESULTS (WITH ALKALI)

Temp. 24°, ionic strength 0.15, conc. of arachin 4.8 g/l				
OH ⁻ added (Moles/1.10 ³)	pH	Free OH ⁻ (Moles/1.10 ³)	Bound OH ⁻ (Moles/mole protein)	Moles of H ⁺ dissociated per mole protein
2.314	8.3	0.0019	159.2	579.2
4.629	10.2	0.15	308.2	728.2
6.924	11.3	1.99	341.58	761.58
13.887	11.9	7.9	412.4	832.4
23.14	12.25	17.78	369.65	789.65

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TABLE 2—pH MEASUREMENT RESULTS (WITH ACID)

Temp. 30°, ionic strength 0.15, conc. of Arachin 4.8 g/l

H ⁺ added (Moles/1.10 ³)	pH	Free H ⁺ (Moles/1.10 ³)	Bound H ⁺ (Moles/mole protein)	Moles of H ⁺ dissociated per mole protein
26.04	1.7	19.95	420	0
17.09	1.95	11.22	411.7	8.3
13.06	2.1	7.9	353	67
8.35	2.3	5.01	229.1	190.9
6.49	2.54	2.88	248.9	171.1
3.72	2.75	1.77	134.48	285.52
1.82	3.0	0.794	70.75	394.25
0.00	6.6	0.0002	0	420

pH MEASUREMENT RESULTS (WITH ALKALI)

Temp. 30°, ionic strength 0.15, conc. of arachin 4.8 g/l

OH ⁻ added (Moles/1.10 ³)	pH	Free OH ⁻ (Moles/1.10 ³)	Bound OH ⁻ (Moles/mole protein)	Moles of H ⁺ dissociated per mole protein
2.314	8.1	.0013	159.3	579.3
4.629	9.9	.079	313.7	733.7
6.943	11.2	1.58	369.7	789.7
13.887	11.8	6.30	523.24	943.24
23.145	12.25	17.78	369.65	789.65

TABLE 3—pH MEASUREMENT RESULTS (WITH ACID)

Temp. 40°, ionic strength 0.15, conc. of arachin 4.8 g/l

H ⁺ added (Moles/1.10 ³)	pH	Free H ⁺ (Moles/1.10 ³)	Bound H ⁺ (Moles/mole protein)	Moles of H ⁺ dissociated per mole protein
26.04	1.69	20.02	415.2	0
17.95	2.0	10.98	414	6.0
13.06	2.1	7.94	353	67
8.34	2.3	5.012	229.1	190.9
6.49	2.4	3.981	173.2	246.8
3.72	2.59	2.57	79.2	340.8
1.82	3.0	1.0	56.55	363.45
0.00	6.5	0.0002	0	420

pH MEASUREMENT RESULTS (WITH ALKALI)

Temp. 40°, ionic strength 0.15, conc. of arachin 4.8 g/l

OH ⁻ added (Moles/1.10 ³)	pH	Free OH ⁻ (Moles/1.10 ³)	Bound OH ⁻ (Moles/mole protein)	Moles of H ⁺ dissociated per mole protein
2.314	8.3	0.0019	159.2	519.2
4.629	9.9	0.079	305.5	725.5
6.943	11.2	1.99	341.58	761.58
13.887	11.9	7.99	412.3	832.3
23.145	12.26	17.0	420.0	840

The pH measurements were carried out at three different temp viz., 24, 30 and 40° by keeping the cell in a water thermostat. Typical results are recorded in Tables 1 to 3 and are graphically represented (Fig. 1).

Calculation :

The number of equivalent of H⁺ ions which are bound when a protein is brought from the isoionic conditions to a state in which all dissociable groups have assumed their acidic forms is equal to the number of cationic acid groups in the molecule

while the equivalent of hydrogen ion dissociated between the isoionic and fully basic state of protein are equal to the number of anionic basic groups⁹.

Fig. 1. Titration curve of arachin at 24°, ionic strength 0.15.

The apparent heat of ionization (ΔH_{ion}) was determined according to Wyman's method¹⁰ using the equation

$$H_{ion} = -2.303 RT^2 \left(\frac{dpH}{dt} \right)$$

The apparent heat of ionization, ΔH_{ion} , was plotted against the number of protons dissociated per protein molecule (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. The relation between the apparent heat of ionization and the number of protons dissociated per protein molecule.

Discussion

The titration curve (Fig. 1) consisted of three main parts corresponding to the groups which titrate in the acid, neutral and alkaline regions,

The titration curve approached a limiting value of hydrogen ions bound at pH 2 where all carboxyl groups were in their acidic form. The pH 6.5 indicates that all carboxylic groups were in their basic forms. Thus the total number of carboxyl group is 420. It was interesting to note that the carboxyl region showed again a break at pH 3.2, since no other titrable groups except glutamic and aspartic acid, are expected¹¹. The portion between pH 2 to 3.2 corresponded to aspartic acid residue (360) and that between 3.2 to 6.5 corresponded to glutamic acid (60) residue. These values were in agreement with those obtained from arachin assay¹² giving the value of 347 and 65 for aspartic and glutamic acid, respectively.

The second part of the titration curve from pH 6.5 to 8 corresponded to neutral region indicating the dissociation of imidazolium groups of histidine. The number of imidazolium groups is 130, which is a bit higher than that obtained from assay. This is perhaps due to the fact that

- (1) the maximum hydrogen ion binding capacity includes also the contribution of an uncertain fraction of the histidine residue,
- (2) the dissociations are not easily distinguishable from those of the phenoxyl group of tyrosine and sulphhydryl group of cystine, since they occur in overlapping range of pH, and

- (3) the titration with base is generally incomplete.

The third main part of the titration curve from pH 8 to 12 indicates the number of basic groups to be 230. It includes mainly lysine and arginine with side chain amino groups, with a contribution from phenolic, sulphhydryl, ammonium and guanidinium groups.

The plot of apparent heat of ionization ΔH_{ion} against the number of proteins dissociated per protein molecule (Fig. 2) shows the expected range^{5,11} of ionizable groups in arachin and lends support to the above results.

Copper and zinc metal binding studies with polarography :

The manual polarograph was used. A H-shaped polarographic cell was found suitable for deaeration of protein solution without denaturation. Nitrogen gas (purified) was passed for about 15 to 20 min to ensure an inert atmosphere. Triply distilled mercury (A.R.) was used for dropping mercury electrode. The capillary used had a flow rate of about 2.2 mg/sec with a drop time of 3.5 sec.

Since the capillary characteristics (m, t) have a marked effect on diffusion current (which is directly proportional to $m^{2/3} t^{1/6}$), these factors were controlled carefully throughout these experiments.

The pH of the buffers and mixture of metal and protein solutions were measured by pH meter using a wide range glass electrode.

Fig. 3. Effect of protein concentration on diffusion current.

Reagents and solutions :

Solution of arachin was prepared by dissolving it in double distilled water. Copper sulphate and zinc sulphate (A.R.) were dissolved in double distilled water. Ammonia-ammonium chloride buffers were prepared from 1.0 M solutions of ammonia and ammonium chloride.

Procedure :

The following sets of solution were prepared for polarographic analysis :

- (1) Varying concentration of the protein (0.5, 0.75, 1.25, 1.75 and 2%) were taken in 50 ml conical flasks and 4.5 ml of 0.005M Cu²⁺ solution added. The total volume was made upto 12 ml by adding the requisite volume of water and 1.8 ml of 1M ammonia-ammonium chlo-

ride buffer ($\mu=0.15$). The results, in the form of a graph of protein concentration (%) against $(i_d)/(i_d)_0$, where i_d and i_{d_0} are the diffusion currents of the metal ion, in the presence and absence of the protein, respectively, are shown in Fig. 3.

TABLE 4—CONC. OF Cu²⁺, 1.87×10^{-3} M, pH 9.4

Conc. of protein (%)	i_d	$(i_d)_0$	$i_d/(i_d)_0$	C_b	V_M
0.50	4.6	9	0.51	1.14	76
0.75	3.6	9	0.40	1.37	62.2
1.25	2.5	9	0.28	1.67	42.4
1.75	2.0	9	0.22	1.82	34.3
2.00	1.8	9	0.20	1.86	31.0

Fig. 4. Effect of copper concentration on diffusion current depression (without protein).

Fig. 4.1. Effect of copper concentration on diffusion current depression.

(2) 1 ml arachin, 1.8 ml buffer (pH 9.4) and varying concentration of Cu^{2+} ion, viz. 0.4166, 0.6249, 0.8332, 1.249 and $1.874 \times 10^{-3} M \text{Cu}^{2+}$ were used, keeping the total volume to 12 ml as before. Similar sets without protein were also prepared (Figs. 4 and 4.1).

TABLE 5—CONC. OF THE PROTEIN, 0.5%

Conc. of $\text{Cu}^{2+} \times 10^{-3} M$	i_a	$(i_a)_0$	$i_a/(i_a)_0$	C_b	$V_{1/2}$
0.520	2.2	1.8	0.4	0.520	34.6
0.624	2.8	2.3	0.6	0.416	27.4
0.833	3.3	2.7	0.8	0.277	18.4
1.24	4.8	3.0	0.85	0.31	20.6
1.87	6.9	3.3	0.9	0.311	20.6

(3) Similarly, at a given concentration of copper sulphate ($0.624 \times 10^{-3} M$) and the protein (0.5%), ammonium buffers of varying pH, viz. 11, 10, 9, 4, 6.1 and 2.6 were taken making the total volume 12 ml by the addition of water. The ionic strength was thus maintained at 0.15. Similar sets without protein was also prepared (Figs. 5 and 5.1).

FIG. 5.

(4) (i) At pH 9.6, varying concentration of zinc sulphate, viz. $3.33, 5.66$ and $8.9 \times 10^{-4} M$ were taken with 2.5% protein in pyrex conical flasks. Another similar set without protein was also prepared. The total volume was made upto 15 ml with water and potassium chloride (to make ionic strength 0.15) solution (Fig. 6).

Fig. 5.1. Effect of pH on diffusion current depression.

Fig. 6. Effect of zinc concentration on diffusion current depression.

TABLE 6—CONC. OF THE PROTEIN 0.5%, CONC OF $Cu^{2+} 624 \times 10^{-2}$.

pH	i_a	$(i_a)_0$	$i_a/(i_a)_0$	C_b	V_M
11	0.81	1.8	0.45	0.624	41.6
10	0.84	1.8	0.47	0.601	40.7
9.4	1.9	1.8	0.5	0.567	37.8
6.1	1.3	1.8	0.74	0.294	19.6
3.6	1.44	1.8	0.8	0.226	15.0

TABLE 7—CONC. OF THE PROTEIN 2.5%, pH 9.4

Conc. of $Zn^{2+} \times 10^{-4} M$	i_a	$(i_a)_0$	$i_a/(i_a)_0$	C_b	V_M
0.89	5.1	8.0	0.62	0.845	10.5
0.56	4.7	6.4	0.75	0.35	4.3
0.33	3.9	4.7	0.82	0.148	1.8

rent pHs from pH 2.6-11 were taken and the volume was made upto 15 ml by adding water and potassium chloride. Similar sets without protein were also prepared (Figs. 7 and 7.1).

(ii) Similarly, 1.5 ml of $8.33 \times 10^{-4} M Zn^{2+}$ solution, 1 ml protein and 1.8 ml buffer of diffe-

Fig. 7. Effect of pH on diffusion current depression (with protein).

Fig. 7.1. Effect of pH on diffusion current depression (without protein).

TABLE 8—CONC. OF THE PROTEIN 2.5%, CONC. OF Zn²⁺ 8.33 × 10⁻⁴ M

pH	i _a	(i _a) ₀	i _a /(i _a) ₀	C _b	V _M
11	6.2	3.3	0.5	0.833	10.4
10	4.3	3.2	0.8	0.333	4.1
9.4	3.2	2.9	0.87	0.216	2.7
6.1	2.5	2.2	0.94	0.099	1.2
2.6	2.1	1.8	0.95	0.083	1.0

(iii) Varying concentrations of the proteins (0.5, 1.2, 2.0, 2.3 and 2.5%) were taken in 50 ml conical flasks and 4.5 ml of 8.33 × 10⁻⁴ M Zn²⁺ solution were added. The total volume was made upto 15 ml by adding water and potassium chloride (Fig. 8).

Fig. 8. Effect of protein conc. on diffusion current.

TABLE 9—CONC. OF Zn²⁺ 8.33 × 10⁻⁴ M, pH 9.4

Conc. of protein (%)	i _a	(i _a) ₀	i _a /(i _a) ₀	C _b	V _M
0.5	6.1	3.5	0.55	0.833	35
1.2	6.1	3.6	0.57	0.795	19.8
2.0	6.1	3.7	0.61	0.721	12.0
2.3	6.1	4.6	0.76	0.444	6.3
2.5	6.1	5.7	0.94	0.111	1.3

Discussion

The usual polarographic method for the study of metal complexes from the shift in half wave potential of the metal ion¹³ failed to give precise information regarding the metal protein interaction because of very small variations in E_{1/2} values of

the order of 0.01 V. Tanford's method^{14,15}, with all its limitations, could however be advantageously employed. Since the copper arachin complex (blue in colour) and zinc arachin complex are formed only at higher pH ranges, the adsorption effects usually encountered could be assumed to exert the minimum influence and the decrease in the ratio i_a/(i_a)₀ can be safely taken as a measure of the extent of metal ion complexed with the protein.

The decrease in the i_a/(i_a)₀ values at pH 9.4, determined experimentally, provides enough information regarding the binding of Cu²⁺ and Zn²⁺ with arachin. From Tanford's equation

$$\frac{i_a}{(i_a)_0} = \frac{C + KC_b}{C_0}$$

where C and C_b are the conc. of free and bound copper or zinc, C₀ its total concentration and K a constant which can be evaluated from the limiting values of i_a [K for set (a) is 0.2], the amount of bound copper can be found. The amount of bound zinc can also be obtained similarly. Taking the molecular weight of arachin to be 33,000, the amount of metal bound (V_M) per mole of the protein could be determined. The results are summarised in Tables 4-9. From these, the values of V_M is seen to be approximately 34 at pH 9.4 for Cu²⁺ whereas for Zn²⁺ the value of V_M is 10 at pH 9.4.

Polarographic measurements carried out at different pH values show that the value of V_M ranges between 37-41.6 for the pH range 8.9-11, while at lower pH, V_M ranges between 15-19.6. These results are significant since they show that the amino groups of arachin bind copper ions more strongly than carboxyl groups.

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